

Examining The Forces Behind Socially Conscious Consumer

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Abstract : Moderation in the style of life makes an improper management towards environment. In all over the world, issues of environment like degradation of environment, natural resources extraction and others environmental problems are in increasing trend. Presently, peoples felt the important of environment and initiate to change their behavior towards environmental protection. Those issues have become more critical role in the market for sustaining of business. It is vital for every concern, to advertise their product for attracting the consumers. This paper tries to identify linkage of demographic profile and factors influencing socially conscious. The findings and suggestion of this study helps the companies and policymakers for their better decision making.

Keywords: Socially Conscious Consumer, Buying Behavior, Consumers' Profile

JEL Classification Number : L1, M31, Q1, Q5, D63.

Introduction

Consumer behavior in the food industry has undergone significant changes in recent years, largely driven by growing consumer awareness of environmental, technological, religious, and social concerns (Basha et al., 2015). All over the world, main problem in environment is shrinking natural resources, population growth and pollution challenge. In daily life, many people facing the experiences and heard many news about both the poor manage and the handling of the environment. It is increasingly apparent that environmental quality is being degraded (Stern, P. C., 1992). The fight against environmental degradation to be effective, consumers have a key role to play (Borah, Dogbe, Dzandu, & Pomegbe, 2023). If consumers demonstrate a high level of environmental consciousness, by inclining towards green purchases of eco friendly products, firms will be compelled to adopt green practices in their operations (De Silva et al., 2021). Those forces are calling for more responsible action in human behaviour. Every individual needs to change their behavior to less exploitive in the natural resources. Because, many psychologists stated that the individual behavior leads to change in the behavior

of whole society. By this reason the individuals are developing their knowledge towards the environment and responsible activities. public organizations are seeking to stimulate and serve the public interest in social issues such as environmental protection. (**Frederick, E. and Webster, J.R, 1975**). The customers' perception is the base for the Grocery shoppers buying decisions. Quality and price of the product, and product fits into their culture, lifestyle and social consciousness are the Value considers by customers'. The influences of the personal values are increasing in the purchase behavior. Many surveys have identified that the most common increase factor in customers' values sustainability and socially conscious. (**International Markets Bureau, 2012**). Fulfill the expectation of the consumers are the main objective of every organization and the customer satisfactions plays a vital role in success of the business. This insists to identify the segments of the population most likely to support the social responsibility activities. In the past literature the socially conscious consumer behavior can be found under various labels. Socially responsible, ethical, and moral have all been used interchangeably with the term socially conscious (**Caruana, 2007**). In this study, socially conscious consumers / socially responsible consumers are used interchangeable.

Review of Literature

Many reviews relates with Socially Responsible Consumers, Consumer Behavior, Green Marketing, Corporate Social Responsibility were considered as review of literature to this study.

Chaihanchai & Anantachart (2023) made an article and defined green products as products that are less harmful to the ecological environment, including land, water, and air. **Sharma et al., (2023)** analysed and found that green products contribute to environmental protection by eliminating or reducing waste, pollution, or toxins. These products may be organic, herbal, or made from recycled products. **Riva et al., (2022)** summarized that the green consumption is defined as a person's behavioral consideration or concern for the ecological environment during the purchase, usage, and disposal of products after usage.

Lin & Niu (2018) found that there is evidence supporting the direct effect of GCK on GPB (there have been some inconsistencies in past studies. **Kumar and Polonsky (2017)** identified GCK to positively influence pro-environmental attitudes, the effect on purchase intention was found to be statistically insignificant. **Hassan and Mustapha (2010)** found green environmental knowledge has a rather negative effect on pro-environmental attitudes.

Karen L.Becker-Olsen (2006) investigated the effect of corporate social responsibility on consumer behavior. For the purpose of analysis the descriptive statistics, t – test, regression etc. were used. This study identified that high fit companies were better than low fit companies in directed the improvement in consumer belief, attitudes and intensions. **Adamantios Diamantopoulos (2003)** made an attempt to identify the relationship between socio – demographic variables. It was found that the combinations of socio-demographic variables are important for determining the characteristics of the products. **Lois A. Mohr et al (2001)** studied about buying behavior with response to corporate social responsibility of the company. The percentage analysis, descriptive and multiple regressions were used and summaries that the typology of consumers purchasing behavior gives response to corporate social responsibility.

James A.Roberts and Donald R.Bacon (1997) researched about the ecological conscious consumer behavior in the market and suggested to improve ecological standard and efficiency by consider the recycled or packaged more efficiently. **Florian G.Kaiser et al., (1999)** explored that the attitude towards environmental is a powerful tool for the ecological behavior. This study found that only the 40 percent of the variance of ecological behavior has explained by knowledge and values of ecological and the general ecological behavior predicted 60 percent of the behavior. **Tate (1995)** identified that the cause-related marketing can be a useful tool for a company to differentiate themselves from their competitors, which improves the chances consumers will purchase their product. **Alexander Grob (1995)** made an attempt to identify the environmental attitudes and behavior of the people. This study provided the strongest effect on environmental behavior restricted from personal-philosophical values and emotions. **Kay, (1993)** identified that the many companies use CSR to gain a favorable reputation which sometimes allows them to ask a premium for their products and/or services.

Statement of the Problem

Extraction of natural resources and increasing level of pollutions are some of the main problem in this globe, currently. Socially Conscious Consumers are increasing due the awareness of environmental conditions. The knowledge about the environmental responsible activities is increasing among the individuals in their purchasing activities. In this situation, every organization is in the position to extend their environmental performance (**Vasanth, V. et al., 2015**) and identify the demographic profile of the Socially Conscious Consumers. For sustaining the field and increase the market value, it is important to fulfill the expectations of consumers. This study moves towards a step to find the linkages between demographic profile and factors influencing socially conscious consumers.

Research Methodology

The required data were collected in big bazar, shopping mall, departmental store etc. located in Coimbatore, Tamilnadu. This study deals with both the primary data and secondary data. The primary data was collected from 100 respondents by issuing questionnaire. Here the respondents were selected randomly. The secondary data were collected from articles, books, magazines, Internet and other sources. For the purpose of analysis, the tools such as Percentage Analysis, Frequency, Graphical Representation, and Correlation.

Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study are

To find the relationship between demographic profile and factors influence Socially Conscious Consumer.

Hypothesis of the Study

NH₀₁: There is no relationship between demographic profile and factors influence Socially Conscious Consumer.

Limitations of the study

There were some unavoidable limitations as follows.

- ❖ Due to time constraint and cost, the study is restricted to only one city.
- ❖ The study is limited to the 100 respondent of consumers.
- ❖ All the limitations associated with statistical tools are also applicable

Data Analysis and interpretation

Demographic Profile

Chart 1 summaries gender wise details of the respondents. It epitomizes that among the total respondent 60% are male and 40% are female. **Chart 2** pictured the age group of the respondents and explains that 82%, 11%, 5% and 2% of the respondents are belongs to the age group of 19 to 25, 26 to 40, below 18, and 41 to above respectively. The marital status of the respondents is demonstrated in **Chart 3**. It shows that 87% of respondents are single and 13% of respondents are married. The Educational Qualifications of the respondents are represented in **Chart 4**. It indicates that the 47% of respondents are Post Graduate, 25% of respondents are Under Graduate, 22% of respondents are Professionals and other few respondents are higher secondary (5%) and others (1%). **Chart 5** illustrates that 72% of respondents are students, 18% of private employee and other self-employee and government employee respondents are few. From the **Chart 6**, the monthly income of the respondents can be understood. It represents that 41% of respondents are below the income level of Rs.7,500/- and 35% of respondent's monthly income between Rs.7,501/- to Rs.15,000/- and 15% of respondent's monthly income between Rs.15,000/- to RS.30,000/-

Chart 1
Gender of the Respondent

Source: Primary data and created using MS Excel

Chart 2
Age of the Respondent

Source: Primary data and created using MS Excel

Chart 3
Marital Status of the Respondent

Source: Primary data and created using MS Excel

Chart 4
Educational Qualification of the Respondent

Source: Primary data and created using MS Excel

Chart 5
Occupation of the Respondent

Source: Primary data and created using MS Excel

Chart 6
Monthly Income of the Respondent

Source: Primary data and created using MS Excel

Result of Correlation Analysis

Result of Correlation analysis between demographic factors and factors influencing normal buying behaviour

Table 1 summaries the result of correlation among the demographic factors and factors influencing normal buying behavior. It explains that the price and package has significant relationship with gender, like wise marital status and product has significant with product. The other factors show the less relationship between the demographic factors and selected variable. It indicates to accept the Null Hypothesis that there is no relationship between demographic

factors and factors influencing normal buying behavior (except gender with price and package, marital status with product).

Result of correlation analysis between Demographic Factors and reason for buying Socially Conscious Product

Table 2 outlines the result of correlation analysis between Demographic Factors and reason for buying Socially Conscious Product shows the significance relationship between the society and advertisement with gender, likewise educational qualifications with safety for environment. The other does not record any significant relationship the demographic factors and reason for buying socially conscious product. so, the null hypothesis is accepted that there is no significance relationship.

Result of correlation analysis between Demographic Factors and Socially Conscious factors relating to Company in buying products

The relationship between the demographic factors and socially conscious factors relating to company in buying products are summarized in **Table 3**. The result shows that gender has significant with product innovation and social activities. Occupation has significant relationship with ethical disclosure. Thus, null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between demographic factors and socially conscious factors relating to company in buying products is rejected for this variable.

Table 1 Analysis of relationship between demographic factors and factors influencing normal buying behaviour

Factors	Gender	Age	Marital Status	Educational Qualification	Occupation	Monthly Income
Price	0.203*	0.009	-0.016	-0.028	-0.019	-0.168
Place	0.041	0.066	-0.118	0.015	0.099	-0.087
Package	0.263**	0.002	-0.048	0.024	0.039	-0.115
Product	0.062	0.102	-.213*	0.087	0.065	0.04
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Source: Primary Data and Computed using SPSS 20

Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

From the above findings, it is noted that in this study, most of the respondents are male. Further, it is identified that 82% of the respondents belong to the age group of 19 to 25 and most of the respondents are post graduate. It is observed from the study that most of respondents buying product in every 15 days (twice a month). On an average, most of the respondents spend the

more around Rs.1000/- for a month for shopping. It is important to note that in this study there is no significant connection between demographic factors and.

Table 2 Analysis of relationship between Demographic Factors and reason for buying Socially Conscious Product

Factors	Gender	Age	Marital Status	Educational Qualification	Occupation	Monthly Income
Safety for Environment	-0.062	0.064	-0.113	.246*	0.086	-0.072
Feeling as Obligation	-0.109	0.042	-0.097	0.1	-0.024	0.014
Society	.314**	0.058	0.047	0.088	-0.169	-0.027
Rules of Government	-0.062	0.021	-0.134	0.064	0.041	-0.079
Advertisements	.204*	0.029	0.02	0.113	-0.103	-0.042
Voluntary Movement	0.014	0.056	-0.029	0.105	-0.079	-0.018
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Source: Primary Data and Computed using SPSS 20

Table 3 Analysis of relationship between Demographic Factors and Socially Conscious factors relating to Company in buying products

Factors	Gender	Age	Marital Status	Educational Qualification	Occupation	Monthly Income
Production Techniques	0.074	0.088	-0.17	.227*	0.136	-0.011
Product Innovation	.201*	- 0.045	0.077	-0.013	-0.117	-.230*
Social Activities	.209*	- 0.036	0.052	0.005	-0.046	-0.065
Ethical Disclosure	0.092	0.153	-0.189	0.141	.261**	0.03
Green Certification	0.143	0.076	-0.058	0.063	-0.067	-0.172

Recycle Process	0.011	- 0.142	0.112	-0.049	-0.169	-.251*
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Source: Primary Data and Computed using SPSS 20

their social consciousness. From the above findings, it is summarized that the results of this study was based on the selected respondents, sampling areas and applied analytical tools. Further, the demographic factors are randomly compared with the factors of social conscious consumers. This study insists the corporates to involve in social activities and label it on their product, to attract the socially conscious consumer and induce to buy product companies should. At the same time, Government should take measures to ensure the quality of the products and social contribution of the companies

References

- Basha, M. B., Mason, C., Shamsudin, M. F., Hussain, H. I., and Salem, M. A. 2015, Consumers attitude towards organic food. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 31, 444–452.
- Becker-Olsen, K. L., Cudmore, B. A., and Hill, R. P. 2006, The impact of perceived corporate social responsibility on consumer behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 59, 46–53.
- Borah, P. S., Dogbe, C. S. K., Dzandu, M. D., and Pomegbe, W. W. K. 2023, Forging organizational resilience through green value co-creation: The role of green technology, green operations, and green transaction capabilities. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(8), 5734–5747.
- Caruana, R. 2007, A sociological perspective of consumption morality. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 6(5), 287–304.
- Chaihanchai, P., and Anantachart, S. 2023, Encouraging green product purchase: Green value and environmental knowledge as moderators of attitude and behavior relationship. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(1), 289–303.
- Chandra Bose, S., and Vasanth, V. 2008, A study on the shift in the patronized motives in buying household products. *Trends in Kalis Research*, 3(1), 80–85. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2753754>
- Diamantopoulos, A., Schlegelmilch, B. B., Sinkovics, R. R., and Bohlen, G. M. 2003, Can socio demographics still play a role in profiling green consumers? A review of the evidence and an empirical investigation. *Journal of Business Research*, 56, 465–480.
- Grob, A. 1995, A structural model of environmental attitudes and behaviour. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 15, 209–220.
- Hassan, S. H., and Mustapha, Y. A. 2010, Malaysian consumer knowledge and preferred information sources in selecting functional foods. *Journal of Agribusiness Marketing*, 3, 20–39.

International Markets Bureau. 2012, *Socially Conscious Consumer Trends*. Market Analysis Report.

Kaiser, F. G., Wolfing, S., and Fuhrer, U. 1999, Environmental attitude and ecological behavior. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 19, 1–9.

Kay, J. 1993, *Foundations of Corporate Success*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Kumar, P., and Polonsky, M. J. 2017, An analysis of the green consumer domain within sustainability research: 1975 to 2014. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 25(2), 85–96.

Leigh, J. H., Murphy, P. E., and Enis, B. N. 1988, A new approach to measuring socially responsible consumption tendencies. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 8(1), 5–21.

Lin, S. T., and Niu, H. J. 2018, Green consumption: Environmental knowledge, environmental consciousness, social norms, and purchasing behavior. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 27(8), 1679–1688.

Mohr, L. A., Webb, D. J., and Harris, K. E. 2001, Do consumers expect companies to be socially responsible? The impact of corporate social responsibility on buying behavior. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 35(1), 45–72.

Priyanga, V. C. 2012, Role of women entrepreneurs and dynamic capabilities in green building industries. *Proceedings of International Conference on International Challenges of Global Entrepreneurship in the 21st Century*, 56–62.

Riva, F., Magrizos, S., Rubel, M. R. B., and Rizomyliotis, I. 2022, Green consumerism, green perceived value, and restaurant revisit intention: Millennials' sustainable consumption with moderating effect of green perceived quality. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(7), 2807–2819.

Roberts, J. A., and Bacon, D. R. 1997, Exploring the subtle relationships between environmental concern and ecologically conscious consumer behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 40, 79–89.

Sharma, K., Aswal, C., and Paul, J. 2023, Factors affecting green purchase behavior: A systematic literature review. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 32(4), 2078–2092.

Stern, P. C. 1992, Psychological dimensions of global environmental change. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 43, 269–302.

Vasanth, V., Selvam, M., Lingaraja, K., and Ramkumar, R. R. 2015, Nexus between profitability and environmental performance of Indian firms: An analysis with Granger causality. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 5(2), 433–439.

Vinayagamoorthi, V., Murugasen, S., Kasilingam, L., Venkatraman, K., and Mahalingam, G. 2012, Environmental management accounting – A decision making tool. *International Journal of Management*, 3(3), 144–151.

Webster, F. E. Jr. 1975, Determining the characteristics of the socially conscious consumer. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 2(3), 188–196.

